

Quality characteristics of Nutri Probiotic Lahi (Sorghum Puff)

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Introduction

Sorghum is an important food staple in many developing countries. Sorghum can be processed in various value-added products such as poha, semolina, puffs, hurda. Sorghum Puffing is a simple inexpensive traditional food technology. It involves hydrating and incubating the grains followed by heat treatment. High temperature allows grain starch to get pre gelatinised in a short time and the pressure allows the endosperm to expand from bran. In puffed grains lipase enzyme gets deactivated which increases the shelf life of the product. Anti-nutrients like phytic acid content get reduced during puffing. Puffed sorghum are consumed in several states of India as a snack. It is similar in flavour to popcorn.

Nutri Probiotic Lahi is a healthy dish. It is suitable for every age group but more beneficial for early childhood, childhood, pregnancy, lactation period because Nutrition requirements are more in these age groups especially Macronutrients and Micronutrients like Energy, Protein, Iron, calcium etc.

Objectives

- To get more beneficial health benefits from puffed sorghum.
- To get quality nutrition with less physiological activities.

Methods

This study was carried out to compare quality characteristics and physiological activities by using home-made fresh curd and fresh fruits in puffed sorghum. Probiotic potential of lactic acid bacteria presents in home-made curd. As home-made fresh curd added in puffed sorghum probiotic activity increased

Preparation of Nutri probiotic Lahi

Ingredients

- 50 gm Curd (Fresh curd Home prepared is better)
- 02 Medium size Banana (200g)
- 100 gm Jowar Lahi (Sorghum puff)
- Few Raisins (4-5)
- Lemon Juice (1 teaspoon)
- Few curry leaves
- Pomegranates seeds ½ katori
- 02 green chili (chopped or according to individual taste)
- Salt and chaat masala to taste
- Coriander leaves (1 teaspoon)

Method

- Clean wash and keep aside jowar Lahi (sorghum puffs)
- Beat curd properly

Cooking time

No cooking is required. Easy to prepare.

Nutrition value

Curd

Curd	Protein	Calories	Fat	Carbs	Calcium
50g	5.88 g	50	2.1g	1.72g	41.5mg

- Wash and chop finely curry leaves and green chills
- Take a bowl, and add beaten curd, mix well washed Lahi, pomegranate seeds, lime juice, salt and chaat masala.
- Mix well all the ingredients.
- Finally, before serving peel and chop 1 banana mix well in Lahi bowl
- Add raisins and garnish with 1 remaining banana and coriander leaves.

Instructions

- All ingredients should be fresh for making the recipe.
- Use homemade curd.

Curd acts as a great probiotic so it provides stronger immunity. It prevents infections. It makes digestion better. It strengthens bones and teeth health.

Banana

Banana	Protein	Calories	Fat	Carbs	Calcium	Iron	Potassium
200 g	2.57g	210	0.78g	53.9	12mg	0.61mg	845mg

Bananas are one of the most popular fruits worldwide. They contain essential nutrients that can have a protective impact on health. Bananas contain

fiber, potassium, folate and antioxidants. They encourage digestive health.

Jowar Lahi (Sorghum Puff)

Sorghum Puff	Protein	Calories	Fat	Carbs	Dietary fiber	Sodium
100g	08g	380	02g	84g	08 g	160mg

Sorghum is a nutrient packed grain that can be used in many ways. Its rich in vitamins and minerals like B vitamins, magnesium, potassium, phosphorus iron

and Zinc. It is known to be rich in phenolic compounds. Many of which acts as antioxidants.

Raisins

Raisins	Protein	Calories	Fats	Carbs
05	0.08g	08	0.01g	2.06g

Raisins are a healthy dried fruit that one can easily to one diet. Raisins contain essential antioxidants that contribute to eye health. They contain polyphenols that prevent free radical damage.

- It also helps in beating the summer heat and enhances stamina and vitality.
- It keeps the skin youthful, pigment free.
- It has also shown various defence factors like protecting the immune system and regulating it in many ways.
- Banana as a fruit has multitude of health benefits like it is good source of prebiotics that activate friendly probiotics.
- The potential biological activities of banana such as antidiarrheal, ant ulcerative, antimicrobial, antioxidant, hypoglycaemic wound healing antilithiatic and anticancer activity.
- Bananas aid in the body's retention of calcium, nitrogen, and phosphorus, all of which work to build healthy and regenerated tissues.
- some studies show that bananas can help improve your mood whether you have the blues or are suffering from PMS.

Lemon Juice

Lemon is high in vitamin C, a primary antioxidant that helps protect cells from damaging free radicals. It aids in digestion. It prevents bad breath. It promotes hydration in the body.

Curry Leaves

Regular intake of curry leaves impart heart healthy properties by strengthening the heart muscles lowering cholesterol levels.

Pomegranate seeds

Pomegranate are rich in antioxidants and flavonoids. Both of which are known to prevent free radicals from damaging cells.

Green chili

It is loaded with vitamin C and beta carotene. Green chilies are great for healthy eyes, skin and immune system.

Coriander leaves

Coriander leaves are dense in fiber and antioxidants. Daily intake of coriander leaves enhances digestion, spikes metabolism.

Health Benefits of Nutri Probiotic Lahi

- It is high in Protein, Fiber and energy.
- It is rich in iron, vitamin C, vitamin B6, magnesium, calcium.
- As curd contains a lot of good bacteria, it helps in digestion.

Result

The results of the study show that the physiological activity and quality characteristics of adding home made fresh curd and fresh fruits containing puffed sorghum to value added improvement.

References

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